

INTEGRATED MULTI-SCALE MODELLING OF 3D WOVEN STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

The weaving of yarns into complex 3D preforms can introduce considerable crimp and waviness. Moreover, compacting these preforms on tools with complex geometries will introduce additional deformations. These deformations are dependent on the local tool geometry and hence are not periodic in nature. As a result, a 3D woven structure needs to be modelled in its entirety. This paper introduces an integrated multi-scale modelling framework that allows the designer to virtually weave, compact and calculate the mechanical performance of 3D woven structures. The proposed framework consists of two main phases; kinematic and mechanical.

The kinematic phase starts by simulating the weaving process to generate an “as woven” unit cell geometry. This geometry is tessellated to form a complete preform, which is then compacted on the desired tool. For the model of the complete structure, a novel homogenisation technique based on a spatial Voronoi tessellation is employed to create a macro scale mechanical model. 3D woven structures exhibit complex progressive failure mechanisms that can only be predicted at the meso-scale where the yarn geometric features are still maintained. Hybrid meso-macro models are thus employed to maintain accurate representations of the failure behaviour while still being applicable to the structure scale

1. INTRODUCTION

Conventional composites have seen wide use in advanced engineering applications on due to their light weight and enhanced mechanical performance. However, a key drawback of conventional 2D woven composites is the lack of through thickness reinforcements. The absence of a mechanism to transfer stresses through thickness means that 2D composites are susceptible to delamination and impact damage. 3D woven composites are made from multiple layers of fibrous reinforcements, woven together using through thickness binder yarns. These binder yarns introduce through thickness load transfer capability that enhances the material’s energy absorption characteristics, interlayer fracture toughness and impact performance [1-4].

During weaving the interaction between weft and warp yarns from one side and binder yarns from the other side introduces crimp and waviness to the woven preform [5]. Additionally, during preform compaction the interaction between the preform internal fiber architecture and the manufacturing tool introduces additional defects and deformation [6]. Examples of 3D woven defects are shown in Figure [1]. Based on this understanding of the nature of 3D woven structures’ manufacturing process, we can identify two types of internal features. The first are due to weaving, which are periodic in nature and can be predicted using unit cell models under periodic boundary conditions. The second type is the compaction/draping deformation which is dependent on the part final geometry and can be only predicted using a structure scale model. In this paper, models dealing with the unit cell will be called meso-scale models while models dealing with the structural scale are called macro-scale models.

Figure 1: Features and deformations in 3D composites. a) CT-Scan close up on a binder yarn, b) Kinematic model close up on a binder yarn, c) CT- Scan of a finished 3D woven component, d) Kinematic model of a finished 3D woven component, e) Kinematic model showing yarn waviness, f) Kinematic model showing yarn spreading.

The other aspect of modelling 3D woven composite structures, is quantifying the mechanical performance of 3D woven structures containing deformation on the meso and macro scales. Research has shown that in this type of composites damage initiates at the meso-scopic features such as crimp and waviness [7]. Additionally, the interaction between progressive damage and the internal fibre architecture dominates the damage progression and consequently the mechanical response on the macro-scale. This complex coupled interaction between the damage on the meso-scale and structural response on the macro-scale, requires the inclusion of the fibre architecture even for the macro-scale models [8]. As a result, the macro and meso scales in the proposed modelling framework need to be fully coupled to allow for the evolution of the structural response on the macro scale to interact with progressive damage on the meso-scale.

2. MODELLING APPROACH OVERVIEW

Under the proposed framework, two separate modeling phases are identified. A kinematic modelling phase where the internal fiber architecture on the unit cell level and the structure level are predicted. The second phase is a mechanical modelling phase where a multi-scale mechanical model is built, taking into account the internal fibre architecture found from the kinematic models. Figure [2] shows an overview of the proposed modelling framework.

Figure 2. 3D woven structures modelling framework

The kinematic modelling phase starts with a unit cell weaving simulation using the digital element approach. The input to the weaving simulation is the fiber architecture and the geometric information of the yarns used in the simulation such as the number of fiber and the fiber diameter. The output from this phase is the unit cell as-woven geometry. Next, the high fidelity geometry is transformed to a single surface representation and then tessellated to form a 3D woven preform of any required size. The preform kinematic model is then combined with the tooling geometry in a contact model to simulate preform compaction to predict the final fibre architecture on the structural scale.

The detailed internal fibre architecture on the structure scale is the entry point to the mechanical modelling phase. Initially, a set of equivalent 3D orthotropic material properties are calculated from the geometry, based on the Intra Yarn Volume Fraction (IYVF) at each yarn cross-section. A homogenized macro-scale model of the structure taking into account the internal fiber architecture is built using 3D spatial Voronoi tessellation. Next, the homogenized model can be solved under the problem loads and boundary conditions to find the critical locations within the structure. Areas that are shown as critical by the macro-model can be replaced by a high fidelity meso-scale model. The two scales are then connected using Lagrangian multipliers. The hybrid meso/macro model can then be solved to provide a high definition prediction of the stresses in the regions of interest, which are suitable for applying damage models.

3 UNIT CELL AS-WOVEN FIBRE ARCHITECTURE

In a digital element simulation, yarns are represented by bundles of beam elements in a contact model [9-11]. The simulation starts with a unit cell model where the yarns are interlaced following the weave style in a loose configuration. The model is under periodic boundary conditions, which are selected based on how the unit cells tessellate to form a full fabric. A dedicated geometric pre-processor is used to generate this loose configuration. During the simulation, thermal load is applied to the binder yarns, which contract, pulling the fabric layers together and simulating the weaving process.

The presence of contact conditions allows for the bundles of beam elements to interact and deform to accommodate the continuously decreasing fabric thickness as the simulation progresses. Once the desired as-woven thickness is achieved the simulation is stopped. Figure [3] shows the digital element simulation progress for a 5 harness orthogonal satin weave. Figure [4] shows a comparison between a Computer Tomography (CT) X-ray scan and digital element simulation for a layer to layer weave style.

Figure 3. Weaving simulation of a 3D woven orthogonal 5 harness satin weave

Figure 4. Comparison between experimental CT scan and digital element model for a layer to layer interlock fabric

4 MACRO-SCALE FIBRE ARCHITECTURE

The digital element approach presented in the previous section is reasonably accurate and suitable for 3D woven fabrics. However, due to the presence of numerous contacts between the bundles of beam elements in a digital element simulation, this approach is computationally expensive and cannot be applied to a structural scale compaction problem. An alternative approach to the digital element is the single yarn surface approach [12]. Yarn surfaces are extracted from the digital element model by fitting a surface around each bundle of beams. Thus, representing each yarn with a single contact surface. The extracted yarn surfaces are then meshed using shell elements. To avoid excessive unrealistic through thickness deformation a visco-elastic core is introduced to the inside of each yarn cross-section to avoid excessive yarn crushing deformation. A mesh of the tooling surface is then added to the model. Rigid material properties are used to model solid tooling and elastic material properties can be used to model a vacuum bag. The single surface fabric model is compacted in a contact model on the tooling of choice. The simulations are normally controlled by tooling displacement. However, in the case of vacuum bag compaction, pressure is also applied to the bag surface. Figure [5] shows a comparison between CT scan and simulation results for a curved structure. The comparison has shown that kinematic models are capable of predicting the yarn paths, cross-

sections, waviness and crimp with a good degree of accuracy. Figure [6] shows a simulation of a double curvature structure.

Figure 5. Comparison between CT scan and simulation for a curved component

Figure 6. Simulation for double dome compaction

5 MESO-SCALE MECHANICAL MODELING

Based on the detailed geometry calculated during the kinematic modeling phase, high fidelity meso-scale mechanical models can be built. Initially, the IYVF is calculated for each section within a yarn. The IYVF is calculated by building a triangulation of the yarn surface to calculate the volume enclosed inside the yarn surface. Next, this volume is compared to the volume of the fiber used to weave the yarn initially. A set of 3D orthotropic material properties are calculated for each cross section, based on the IYVF, along the yarn path [13]. The material axis for each cross-section is calculated as the tangent to the yarn path at a given cross-section. The meshing method of choice for this approach is Voxelization since it is a robust meshing method capable of handling the complex geometries of realistic 3D woven fabric. The problem domain is initially divided into Voxels of the desired density. Next, Voxels located inside a yarn surface are assigned the 3D orthotropic material properties and material axis associated with the yarn at this location. After all yarns are mapped to

Voxels, the remaining Voxels are assigned homogeneous matrix properties. Figure [7] shows the properties mapping results to a Voxel mesh. Figure [8] shows the IYVF distribution for a 3D woven composite. The high fidelity meso-scale models can be solved under any combination of loads and boundary conditions to generate a detailed prediction of the stresses and strains. Consequently, damage models can be applied on this scale. Figure [9] and [10] shows the stress distribution for a 3D woven composite under tensile loading.

Figure 7. materials mapping of 3D woven composite

Figure 8. Intra yarn volume fraction for a 3D woven composites

Figure 9. Loading direction stresses for a 3D woven composite

Figure 10. Transverse direction stresses for a 3D woven composites

6 MACRO-SCALE MECHANICAL MODELLING

A key challenge with 3D woven structure macro-modeling, is the lack of a basis of homogenization such as layers or plies found in 2D composites. Additionally, in the case of a 3D woven structure with complex geometric features, the periodicity is lost due to fabric deformation and unit cells can no longer be used as basis of homogenization [12]. Here we introduce a novel homogenization approach based on Voronoi tessellation [14-16]. Conventional Voronoi tessellation divides a domain into interlocking cells. Each cell represents a region of influence for a geometric center. In the proposed approach, the traditional Voronoi tessellation is expanded to the 3D case by using the yarn surfaces as tessellation generators. Using the 3D Voronoi tessellation the problem domain is divided into an exhaustive and mutually exclusive set of sub-domains where each domain represents the region of influence of a yarn. The material properties within each region can be then homogenized using volume integration. This homogenization approach can reduce the number of degrees of freedom in a model by an order of magnitude. Figure [11] shows the result of the 3D Voronoi tessellation as applied to a 3D woven 5 harness satin weave. Figure [12] shows a comparison of the transverse strain distribution on the surface of 3D woven tensile sample between an experimental DIC, meso-scale model and macro-scale model. Table [1] shows a comparison between the elastic moduli of the 3D woven samples as predicted by meso models, macro models and experiments. The comparison with experimental results show that the homogenized model accurately predict the stiffness response of 3D woven composites.

Figure 11. 3D Voronoi tessellation as applied to a 3D woven 5 harness satin weave

Figure 12. A comparison of transverse strain on a 3D woven tensile sample.

Engineering Constant	Experimental (GPa)	Meso-Scale (GPa)	Macro-Scale (GPa)
Young's modulus warp	63.9	64	63
Young's modulus weft	60.8	61	60
In-plane shear modulus	4.65	4.75	4.3

Table 1: Comparison of elastic moduli predict by simulations against experimental results

7 MULTI-SCALE MECHANICAL MODELLING

Up to this point, two separate sets of mechanical models have been presented. A high fidelity modeling approach where damage models can be applied and a homogenized macro model approach

where the stiffness response is maintained. Multi-scale modelling has seen wide application in modelling composite material behaviour [17]. Additionally, global/local analysis has been used effectively to model progressive damage in composites [18]. An efficient approach to mechanical modelling of 3D woven structures is to combine meso and macro models in a global/local analysis. Initially, a complete macro-scale analysis is carried out. Next, the highly loaded areas within the structures are determined from the macro results. Those highly loaded region are replaced with high fidelity meso-scale models. The meso-scale nodes located on the interface with the macro models are identified using a convex hull applied to the meso mesh. A velocity/ displacement compatibility condition and a stresses compatibility condition are enforced on the interface nodes to connect the two scales. The displacement/velocity compatibility condition is introduced to the simulation by defining the meso-scale interface displacements/velocities in terms of the macro-scale interface displacement. Each meso-scale node is related to an element face on the macro-scale using a Lagrangian multiplier equation linking the macro-face and meso-node's degrees of freedom. The force terms from the Lagrangian multipliers are fed back to the macro-scale to enforce the stresses compatibility condition on the interface. The meso-model, macro-model and Lagrangian multiplier now form a multi-scale system. An iterative solver is used to solve the three systems of equation simultaneously.

Figure [13] shows an example of a complex 3D woven component. The section of the component which shows the highest level of crimp and deformation is selected for multi-scale modelling. An initial macro-scale model based on Voronoi homogenization is used to determine the critical regions within the component. The macro-scale model, which is loaded in compression in the Y axis direction, is shown in Figure [14]. Next, the model is decomposed into meso and macro zones based on the macro model results. Figure [15] shows the domain decomposition. Figure [16] shows the final results of the multi-scale simulation for the meso-scale domain.

Figure 13. A kinematic model of a complex 3D woven component.

Figure 14. Macro-scale modelling of a complex 3D woven structure, a) Voronoi homogenization b) strain in loading direction

Figure 15. Multi-scale model domain decomposition

Figure 16. a) 3D woven properties mapping for meso-scale model. b) Loading direction stress for the meso-scale model. c) Through thickness shear stress for the meso-scale model.

8 CONCLUSIONS

A comprehensive multi-scale technique for modelling 3D woven composite structure is presented. The proposed framework consists of two multi-scale phases. An initial kinematic phase where the 3D fabric as-woven and compacted internal fibre architecture is found. Next, a multi-scale mechanical modelling phase uses the detailed fibre architecture to build a hierarchal prediction of the stress state within the structure. Both the kinematic and mechanical models have been compared to experimental results with good agreement. The inputs and outputs for each modelling phase have been identified with the various links between the modelling scales. The integrated multi-scale modelling framework provides a high fidelity prediction of the stress state in critical locations throughout the structure. As a result, it is now feasible to embark on progressive damage modelling on the macro-scale.

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